

CONTINUOUS PHASE AND MEANS OF USE IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya. *O‘zbek tilida davomiylik faza odatda analitik konstruksiya yordamida ifodalanadi. Davomiylik faza ma’nosining aspekt qiymatlari bilan bog‘langan variantlari ham analitik tarzda ifodalanadi. Maqolada fe’llarning to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri leksikasi, davomiy zamon, ravishlar, analitik konstruksiyalar va qo‘shma fe’llar kabi turli xil vositalar yordamida ifodalash ma’nolari ko‘rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *davomiylik faza, birikmalar, faza davomiyligi, harakat, boshlanish, aniq holatni saqlab qolish, harakatni takrorlash, bir vaqtdan ikkinchisiga yo‘naltirish, reja.*

Аннотация. *Фаза продолжение в узбекском языке обычно выражается с помощью аналитической конструкции. Аналитически выражаются и варианты значения продолжительной фазы, связанные со значениями аспектов. В статье рассматриваются значения, выражаемые с помощью различных средств, таких как прямая лексика глаголов, длительное время, формы, аналитические конструкции и сложные глаголы.*

Ключевые слова: *фаза продолжение, соединения, продолжительность фазы, действие, начало, решение, сохранение состояния, повторение действия, направление от одного времени, плана к другому.*

Abstract. *Continuous phase in Uzbek language is usually expressed using an analytical construction. Variants of the continuous phase meaning associated with aspect values are also expressed analytically. The article considers the meanings about expressing through various means, such as direct lexicon of verbs, continuous tense, forms, analytical constructions and compound verbs.*

Keywords: *continuous phase, compounds, phase duration, action, beginning, preclude, preservation of a state, the repetition of an action, the direction from one time, plan to another.*

Introduction. In Uzbek language, the continuous phase is usually expressed using an analytical construction. By analytical construction, we mean compounds verbs formed with auxiliary verbs. The meaning of pure continuation, which is not connected with the values of the aspect (kind, hue), that is, the meaning of the continuation of the process that started and was interrupted for some reason, is not expressed in the Uzbek language in a synthetic form (through a single verb). This meaning is expressed by the compounds *to continue (to be continued)*.

Research methodology. *The continuous phase is expressed by the combination of a noun (to continue) and an auxiliary verb (to do). Variants of the continuous meaning associated with aspect values are also expressed analytically. In such analytical compounds, if the meaning of the process is covered by the transitive form of the verb (-ib), the aspectual signs associated with the meaning of phase duration are connected with auxiliary verbs. Verbs of different types can be used as helpers: stand, sit, stay, expressing the situation; walking action verbs (verbs such as to walk, to go, to come) participating not in their own meaning, but in the transitive meaning.*

Pay attention to the examples: *someone is working (reading...), they are talking, he is reading the newspaper, he is writing a letter, he was writing something (compound verb structure), Days went by days (context).*

Analysis and results. The verb *to go* can have meanings related to the duration phase. Continue: *I'm knitting a scarf, by going to school (songs), G'ijim ro'mol to 'qiyman, maktab borib o'qiyman (qo'shiqlar) There's a heated conversation. Days went by. Qizg'in suhbat boryapti. Kunlar ketidan kunlar borardi.* The leading verb indicates the gradual development of the action expressed: *The wind is getting stronger. The patient's condition is improving. The morning is breaking. As time passed, Prophecy could feel her sister changing before her eyes.* [2,132]. Shamol kuchayib borayotir. Bemorning ahvoli yaxshilanib boryapti. Tong yorishib bormoqda. Vaqt o'tib bormoqda, Bashorat singlisining ko'z o'ngida o'zgarib borayotganini sezardi. (A.Muxtor. Opa-singillar [2,132].

The leading verb - (i) *b* with the adverbial form denotes the continuation and development of an action or the accompanying progress of an action. For example: *ahvoli yaxshilanib bormoqda*, [8, 75]. *His condition is getting better* [8,75].

The verb *to come* - (i) combined with the leading verb in the adverbial form, is used as an auxiliary verb and indicates the action that has been going on for a long time: *Nurining buyruqlariga so'zsiz bo'ysunib kelgan Gulnor, hech nima o'ylamasdan o'rnidan turdi (Oybek, Qutlug'qon); Gulnor, who obeyed Nuri's orders without a word, came up without thinking about anything (Oybek, Kutlugkhan); Men bu sirni shu choqqacha ichimda saqlab kelayotgan edim, endi aytnasam bo'lmaydi* [2, 378]. *I have been keeping this secret inside me until now, now I need tell it* [2,378].

When the leading verb combined with the adverbial form –(i) *b*, *to come* represents an action that continues for a certain period of time. For example: *Bu kitobni o'qib kelmoqdaman; Men bu sirni shu choqqacha ichimda saqlab kelayotgan edim, endi aytnasam bo'lmaydi. I have been reading this book ; I have been keeping this secret inside me until now, and now I can't tell it.*

It is included in the group of compound verbs in the form of adverb: *to come and stand* [8,206].

The verb *to go* can also mean the continuation of the action, of the process duration, the beginning and the continuation. For example: *Davom etmoq: Imtihon ketayapti. Majlis ketayapti. O'rmonjon, odatda, ish sustroq yoki yomonroq ketayotgan uchastkalarga borar edi; Harakatni davomiyligi: Otabek ... yangi va eshitilmagan fikrlarni so'zlab ketdi.* [5, 383]; *Continue: The exam is going on. The meeting is going. The forester usually went to the sections where the work was slower or worse; Continuity of action: Otabek ... spoke new and unheard thoughts* [5, 383]; In the function of an auxiliary verb, when it is attached to the form of the adverb with the affix –a / ay, it indicates the beginning and continuation of the action quickly and strongly: *Samandarov ... qo'lidagi qog'ozni Boltaboyga berib, unga allanimani tushintira ketdi.* [5,383]. *Samandarov ... gave the paper in his hand to Boltaboy and went to explain to him the name.* [5, 383].

Went comes as an auxiliary verb and expresses the permanence, repetition or duration of the action. *The clock is ticking. Come back often. I see him every day. Water flows in this stream in winter and summer. He (Mahmoud Torabi) worked with his two brothers, Muhammad and Ali, from dawn to dusk, making a big living. (M. Osin, The story of our ancestors). Ikramjon turned and looked at him (Nizamjon). Drops of tears were trembling on his gray beard. (S. Ahmad, Ufq). To carry. Constantly receiving, always receiving. The old man was receiving a pension.* (receiving is combined with various lexical-semantic verbs in this function (walking is an action, i.e.

procedural or interactive actions that occur at the same time (*to swing, to flow, to carry* - additional verb).

-(i) *b* comes in the adverbial form with the affix and indicates that the action is continuing at the same time with the preceding adverbial. *Study while working. On the way, I remembered you. He was surprised while reading the column. The wrestler picked up the stag that had come out on his shoulder, held it by both ends, and turned it around a couple of times.* [8,227].

It was getting dark in the desert, everyone was gathered, drinking tea in the big tent, by the light of the stone lantern, and he was talking from side to side. (S. Ahmad, *Ufq*).

Another (leading) verb *has* –*ib* acting as an auxiliary verb with the adverbial form means the duration of the action and its extension: *I will not talk much about this; there is no need to think about it for a long time* [8,619].

to stretch is directly related to the duration phase and is explained by the combination - "*to continue*". Look at the examples given in the dictionary: *My conversation with the moon continued for a long time, and the morning came. (Enthusiastic). Tantiboivachcha, having finished the night's party and drinking with a long sleep, continued of the castle door to the garden. (Oybek, Kutlug qon).*

The verb combined to prolong with nouns indicates the continuous of the action (*process*) they express: *the meeting was prolonged, the construction period is lengthening, the conversation was prolonged* [8,550]. It also indicates continuity in the adverbial form.

First of all, this verb is not used as an auxiliary verb, but always retains its lexical meaning.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In short, the semantic scope of the continue phase includes *the preservation of a state, the repetition of an action, the direction from one time, plan to another*, includes meanings such as *prolongation of movement, continuation of interrupted movement*. These meanings can be expressed through various means, i.e. direct lexicon of verbs, continuous tense forms, analytical constructions and compound verbs. If the expression of the continuous phase in English is primarily related to the lexical meaning of verbs and long tense forms, in Uzbek language the continuous phase is expressed in most cases with the help of analytic verb combinations.

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